

Autofocus Under Large Defocus Conditions

Abstract:

This paper discusses the current state of research on autofocus under large defocus conditions and conducts experiments on two focusing strategies—linear search and binary search—using commercial cameras with medium-to-telephoto lenses. Based on experimental results and related studies in the literature, the paper suggests that applying AI algorithms such as deep learning to extract additional information from defocused images may be a potential solution for enabling autofocus under large defocus conditions.

Keywords: auto-focus; large defocus; Linear Search; Binary Search

Introduction:

Defocus refers to the condition where the focal point fails to align correctly with the subject, resulting in a blurred image. Large defocus is an extreme case of this, where the focal point is significantly misaligned, producing severe blur. In such situations, the lens may not detect sufficient contrast or phase differences, causing both phase detection autofocus (PDAF) and contrast detection autofocus (CDAF) algorithms to fail.

During the era of DSLR cameras, camera bodies generally employed aggressive autofocus strategies that continued to attempt focus even under large defocus. However, these often resulted in poor outcomes, including "pumping", where the lens moves back and forth repeatedly due to focus failure, indicating an oscillation problem in the autofocus algorithm.

In the mirrorless camera era, manufacturers (primarily Japanese companies) adopted a more conservative commercial strategy. When autofocus fails under large defocus, the camera typically abandons the focus attempt, leaving the user to rely on experience to manually resolve the issue.

Academic research on this topic has largely focused on specialized applications such as microscopes and Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM). These environments are more controlled, making it possible to extract additional information even under large defocus.

For instance, in TEM, the difference in imaging under under-focus and over-focus conditions can be analyzed, and algorithms like the Gerchberg–Saxton algorithm can be used to reconstruct phase information, aiding in focus recovery.

Reference [2] even introduced laser triangulation for an active focus

mechanism. However, such approaches are entirely impractical for consumer cameras and significantly increase costs for industrial systems as well.

Most researchers are exploring deep learning methods or analyzing optical characteristics under large defocus to extract auxiliary information that can aid in achieving autofocus.

In typical consumer camera scenarios, the optical environment is more complex. Scenes with low contrast, such as plain-colored walls, foggy conditions, or backlighting, frequently cause autofocus failure. Yet in most of these cases, manual focusing can still resolve the issue. This suggests that the problem is not unsolvable but that the autofocus algorithm falls into a classic optimization trap, such as settling on a local rather than a global optimum. Therefore, this paper attempts to analyze the strategies humans use in manual focusing.

Experiment Setup:

Large defocus tends to occur more frequently with medium-to-telephoto lenses, whereas camera systems suited for research usually use wide-angle lenses (such as the Raspberry Pi Camera) or standard lenses with focal lengths below 50mm (as in most industrial camera systems). While some industrial cameras support 85mm lenses, these are typically fully manual.

To facilitate the study of focus strategies, this paper uses a standard commercial full-frame camera and a 70–200mm medium telephoto lens. However, commercial cameras do not provide an open environment for autofocus testing. Thus, manual focusing is used initially to study focus strategies, with future plans to convert them into automated control algorithms on suitable industrial camera systems.

Experimental Steps:

The procedure begins with achieving focus on a near (or far) object, then turning off autofocus and moving the object to the opposite end (far or near). Autofocus is then re-enabled, causing the camera system to enter a large defocus state. As shown in the figure below, the images represent, from left to right, the under-focus, in-focus, and over-focus states. By standardizing the manual recovery process from large defocus back to proper focus, this setup provides a basis for analyzing various autofocus strategies.

Specifically, the goal is to find an appropriate focus position within the range from the minimum focusing distance D to the hyperfocal distance H .

Picture from Alan Ranger Photography

$$H = f + \frac{f^2}{N \times C}$$

where:

- H – Hyperfocal distance;
- f – Focal length of lens used;
- N – Aperture f-number; and
- C – Circle of confusion limit.

Let C take a typical value of 0.0288 mm, which approximately corresponds to a spatial resolution of 5 line pairs per millimeter.

Linear Search Strategy:

In the diopter domain (i.e., $1/\text{distance}$ in meters), the range from $1/D$ to $1/H$ is divided into N evenly spaced points. At each step, the lens group is moved by a distance d to the n -th position, and the original autofocus algorithm is invoked to attempt focusing.

This algorithm simulates the steps a human would take to solve the focusing problem—it is not purely manual focusing but a combination of manual intervention and autofocus.

Test Results:

- Focal length $f=150$ mm
- Minimum focusing distance $D=3$ meters
- Actual object distance = 8 meters

Aperture f-number	Minimum focal range	hyperfocal distance	N	focus start pos dioptries	Focus result	Focus attempt times
4	9.6m	195.5m	20	1/H	success	19
4	9.6m	195.5m	20	1/D	success	2
4	19.2m	195.5m	10	1/D	failed	10
4	24m	195.5m	8	1/D	failed	8
4	38.4m	195.5m	5	1/D	failed	5
11	3.5m	71m	20	1/H	success	18
11	3.5m	71m	20	1/D	success	3
11	7.1m	71m	10	1/D	success	2
11	8.9m	71m	8	1/D	success	2
11	14.2m	71m	5	1/D	failed	5
22	1.8m	35.6m	20	1/H	success	16
22	1.8m	35.6m	20	1/D	success	4
22	3.5m	35.6m	10	1/D	success	3
22	4.5m	35.6m	8	1/D	failed	8
22	7.1m	35.6m	5	1/D	success	2

The algorithm shows a high success rate overall. However, when the initial lens position is on the opposite side of the actual subject distance, more focus attempts are required. Even so, the algorithm avoids repeated refocusing—no focus oscillation occurs, even in the case of failure.

A comparative experiment on aperture (f-number) reveals that a smaller aperture (e.g., F11) significantly improves focusing due to the increased depth of field. However, an excessively small aperture (e.g., F22) introduces diffraction effects that instead degrade focus performance.

Binary Search Strategy:

To accelerate the focus search process and mimic the manual focusing approach, a binary-search-like focusing strategy is tested. Within the range from the minimum focusing distance DDD to the hyperfocal distance HHH, the algorithm performs a binary division by positioning the lens group at the midpoint of each half of the focusing range and attempting autofocus.

However, unlike standard binary search, this strategy requires autofocus attempts at both midpoints of the left and right subranges after each division. If both attempts fail, the contrast data from these two positions is compared to determine which half is more suitable for further focus searching. Given the closed nature of commercial camera systems, contrast data is obtained through single captures followed by computer-based image analysis.

Compared to the linear search strategy, this approach can reduce the number of autofocus attempts under certain test conditions. However, in adverse conditions such as backlighting, it may lead to focus oscillation. This is likely due to the fact that the lens group moves in larger steps, whereas in the linear strategy, movements are incremental.

Test Results:

- Focal length $f=150$ mm
- Minimum focusing distance $D=3$ meters
- Actual object distance = 8 meters

Aperture f-number	hyperfocal distance H	focus start pos dioptries	Focus result	Focus attempt times
4	195.5m	1/H	success	5
4	195.5m	1/D	success	5
11	71m	1/H	success	4
11	71m	1/D	success	4
22	35.6m	1/H	success	2
22	35.6m	1/D	success	2

Low-Light Test Results:

- Focal length $f=150$ mm
- Minimum focusing distance $D=3$ meters
- Actual object distance = 8 meters

Aperture f-number	hyperfocal distance H	focus start pos dioptries	Focus result	Focus attempt times
4	195.5m	1/H	failed	oscillated
4	195.5m	1/D	failed	oscillated
11	71m	1/H	success	4
11	71m	1/D	success	4
22	35.6m	1/H	failed	oscillated
22	35.6m	1/D	failed	oscillated

This strategy shows a promising success rate, and the number of focus attempts is more evenly distributed compared to the linear focusing strategy. However, under low-light conditions, it becomes difficult to reliably determine which half of the focus range is more appropriate, leading to a higher likelihood of severe focus oscillation.

Conclusion:

Large defocus is an extreme blur condition caused by significant deviation of the focal point, essentially reflecting the optical system's inability to compensate for focus

error within its limited adjustment range. In current commercial cameras, autofocus failure under large defocus typically requires manual focusing or manual assistance. This study explored several focus search strategies to address this problem, but neither the linear nor the binary search approach yielded fully satisfactory results.

As noted in the referenced literature, extracting additional information from defocused images is a necessary path toward solving the autofocus challenge under large defocus. Given the complexity of real-world shooting environments and the severe degradation of image quality under large defocus, adopting nonlinear methods—particularly deep learning—appears to be a more promising and viable solution.

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